

The Tourism Industry and Women

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Introduction

ITS hard fact to digest in the 21st century. When we come to know that Women are still being hindered from going for tours Abroad and the risk rate being high most People Discourage women from working in the tourism industry. Safety is one of the Common criteria which every Guardian, parent or relative used to dissuade the women In their family. In these articles to specify some events and facts as to why women are Discouraged from getting employed in tourism industries. Also igniting some Events that have filled the minds of the populace wit fear and misconception.

Contribution in Economic

IT contributes to about 7% of the jobs and 5% of the GDP for the whole world. Though the perks of the tourism Industry are distributed equally in the developed world they are Somewhat unequal in developing countries. Gender inequality and women empowerment explain This concept much better than anything else. It has been often seen that women are employed at lower levels with low Paying jobs that are precarious in the tourism industry. Gender stereotyping and discrimination usually display Women as confined to safe and domestic jobs like cooking, cleaning and hospitality. Here we will discuss why women are the primary prey to Discrimination the except to which tourism industry has helped women meet their needs and the extent to which the tourism industry has tried providing job satisfaction for women.

Women as Primary Prey Discrimination

Women are more likely to work in clerical services in Tourism industries than compete with men at higher and More professional levels in tourism. Because of this, they Are becoming victims of low paying jobs, unable to run Homes efficiently. We see this in one of the report findings By UNWTO submitted and published in 2010. The social Fear of giving women higher job positions has indirectly found them in a state of backwardness. The idea of social fear preventing women from stepping out of their homes In today's culture might seem absurd. But in countries that or backward and undeveloped, it presents a safer option.

There is some statics which shows the extent of Discrimination in hiring women as part of the workforce in the tourism industry.

1. Compared to youth, women have a lower rate of employment opportunity.About 39% of the workforce in the tourism industry.

1. Compared to youth, women have a lower rate of employment opportunity.About 39% of the workforce in Tourism is occupied by the youth,giving little space for Women;
2. Other countries like the Bahamas have only 40% Off the seats reserved for women,whereas in the other 60% is given to women.This 40% of jobs are Relative to role men. All relative to hotel service Sector in tourism,then outdoor jobs which by more.
3. India shows a meagre yet significant 38% of Hiring vacancy for women and men still pay women less.
4. A lot of women working in family tourism Businesses are unpaid.
5. A vast difficult to pay is seen where women earn 15% less salary than men in the tourism industry

Struggles for Women in Tourism

Education is the fundamental weapon for Women. To against discrimination visible in the tourism Industry.The shortage of women in the tertiary level of A proper push to let them grab the brilliantopportunitiesWhich are usually availed by men. The chances for good Proportion of women around theworld to home their Leadership skill is probably why we find A small number of CEOs woo are women in tourism Industries.

One motivating story is a sole female biker named Esha Gupta,who travelled 32000k.m across sixteenStates in India.Though she faced many challenges her Will and determination to complete her arm brought her success.

Socio-Economic Pressure

Poverty may be one significant reason for families To withdraw their girls from pursuing further Education due to which many are deprived of format And informalopportunities in tourism industries.The Tour India has many “own account works” who are Women. Dealing with such pressure extended upon them Is quite tough, but one should not ever forget that Women are born strong enough tohope up with Pressers a man can’t face in his lifetime,The tourism Industry should address, gender equality in every area which can help with the community as a choice?

Conclusion

Viewing the status quo of women in the tourism industry,women must be aware of both the positives and negatives of the profession by educating Themselves about other people with experience.to truly Bring about a change,challenges that the tourism Industry lightface Should be predicted and solution should be created in foresight.This might not only Help private sectors around the world, but also public Sectors,international organizations and civil Societies.

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